

Striking the Delicate Balance between International Trade and Environmental Protection: Implications for Climate Change in Oman

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Abstract

International trade law and international environmental law have experienced a different evolution, characterized by the precedence of the international economic order on the development of environmental law. In this paper, relations between international trade and environment have been discussed within its implications at national and internal levels. It was shown that the absence of a firm balance between the two has affected climate change.

For country as Oman who depends mainly on oil and gas sector, the issue of reducing CO2 emission need formulation of strict environmental and energy policies. The government can adopt and encourage the use of renewable energy as best alternatives for oil and gaz.

Keywords: Oman. Climate Change; Environment, International Trade

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1. Introduction

International trade law and international environmental law have experienced a Different evolution, characterized by the precedence of the international economic order on the development of environmental law.

Nowadays, the process of globalization raises ethical, philosophical and political questions on both the development and the evolution of our society vis-à-vis the preeminence of economic logic. Analyzing the highly complicated question of relations between trade and environment is, thus, as indispensable as it is incredibly difficult.

In this paper, relations between international trade law and international environmental law, two branches that have developed independently within the international legal system, will be explored with particular reference to how the absence of a firm balance between the two has affected climate change.

Climate change is one of the greatest challenges facing the international community. Mitigating global warming and adapting to its consequences will require major economic investment and, above all, unequivocal determination on the part of all policy-makers.

2. The Interrelationship between International Trade and Environmental Protection

Global awareness of international trade and environmental concerns were beginning interested at the United Nations Stockholm Conference on Development in 1972 and has been a key aspect of the Brundtland Report¹. This report was published in 1987 by the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED). At the Stockholm Conference, development was linked to the exploitation of natural resources; in the Brundtland Report interdependence appeared as a central element, recognizing the existing interconnection between political spheres that by then were governed by different rules and institutions (such as industry, species and genetic resources protection, energy, etc.).

¹ The Brundtland Report introduced the concept of sustainable development and described how it could be achieved sponsored by the united nations (UN) and chaired by Norwegian Prime Minister Cro Harlem Brundtland.

In the scope of the Rio Conference, the right to development was related to the Imperatives of environmental protection. The 1992 World Conference on Environment and Development provided a generally accepted definition of the concept of sustainable development, elaborating different concepts and approaches of development that takes into account its economic, environmental and social aspects. Despite the lack of a generally accepted definition in a binding agreement, the Conference clearly established the links between economic development, mainly composed by trade, and environmental rules in the scope of social conditions.

The right to development must be fulfilled so as to equitably meet developmental and environmental needs of present and future generations. (Principle 3, Rio Declaration, 1992) In order to achieve sustainable development, environmental protection shall constitute an integral part of the development process and cannot be considered in isolation from it. (Principle 4, Rio Declaration, 1992)

In Agenda 21, the responsibility of states in the implementation of a development policy was detailed as follows:

Governments recognize that there is a new global effort to relate the elements of the international economic system and mankind's need for a safe and stable natural environment. Therefore, it is the intent of Governments that consensus-building at the intersection of the environmental and trade and development areas will be ongoing in existing international forums, as well as in the domestic policy of each country. (Agenda 21, Chapter 2)

Seen from the perspective of free trade, the relation between trade and environment presents itself as follows:

- Trade sets the conditions for economic growth that are necessary to improve human well-being and, therefore, well-being of the environment;
- Trade may be used to improve conditions for environmental protection by allowing the exchange of knowledge and environmental-friendly production techniques or by fostering the use of less polluting means of production;
- Trade may avoid waste by enabling the distribution of production.

The environmental perspective of the relations existing between trade and environment may vary depending on the preferred theoretical approach and the level of radicalism of the pursued goals. The trading system is generally considered to be a threat to the environmental equilibrium, since: this general approach is not enough to solve frequent conflicts between these two normative branches and, above all, to analyze in depth the contradictions between the international trading system on the one hand and the establishment of a development model favoring the environment on the other. Thus, the opposing sides of both normative branches confront the international legal order.

The main problem is to evaluate the effects derived from the interrelationship existing between trade and environment². In order to better command the relation between these two fields, some organizations such as the WTO or OECD have created working groups to develop methods to evaluate the impact of liberalization of trade on the environment and vice versa (i.e. methods likely to measure the effects of liberalization of trade on the environment). Such initiatives, still very recent, do not provide precise and exhaustive results on every sector of activity. For example, analyses are ongoing on agriculture and the impact of fisheries and forestry measures within the OECD Joint Working Party on Trade and Environment.

Confronted by the reality of trade liberalization, international environmental law has adopted trade measures aiming to solve different environmental problems at the national and international levels.

The term *trade measures* usually refers to any instrument imposing restraints, conditions or restrictions to both imported or exported products and services, or to the process of their import or export . Trade measures may,

² In the policy arena, the importance of establishing coherent relationships between the trade obligations set out in various bilateral and multilateral trade agreements and environmental policies of countries is now well recognized. Environmental provisions in the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) allow adoption of product-related measures in certain situations if they are “necessary to protect human, animal or plant life or health, “or “relat[e] to the conservation of exhaustible natural resources.” In addition, other trade agreements—such as NAFTA and the U.S.-Singapore free trade agreement—include provisions that directly address environmental concerns.

thus, take a variety of forms from the perspective of establishing an environmental policy: trade bans, product standards, notification procedures, etc. Furthermore, the role of trade measures in different conventions may vary greatly depending on the goals of the conventions and the expected impact of trade relations on the conventions' environmental objectives. It is estimated that there are more than 300 MEAs³ addressing very different environmental problems.

Some of them deal with very specific issues and others concern economic activities. The following categories may be identified in general:

- Agreements aiming to control and monitor trade activities, considering that they contribute to overexploitation of natural resources (animal and plant species, mineral resources, etc.);
- Agreements aiming to combat trade activities seen as sources of pollution (waste, air pollution, etc.).

The Convention on Nature Protection and Wild Life Preservation in the Western

Hemisphere, adopted in Washington, DC, on 12 October 1940, established a control system by issuing certificates authorizing the export, transit and import of certain protected fauna and flora (Article IX).

The African Convention on the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources, adopted in Algiers on 15 September 1968, set measures to rule traffic (transport, trade, exports, etc.) in specimens and trophies through an authorization system for export and import (Article IX). Different annexes permit the establishment of regimes authorizing takings (more strict for species from list A than those from list B, Article VIII.1 do).

This section has shown the ambiguous approach towards the confrontation between the two legal systems that link trade and environment, with no concrete solution being offered to solve the (obvious) difficulties resulting from their coexistence as evidenced in the seeming oblivion to the increasing effects of Climate Change. The next section will examine the global effort to address the impact of trade liberalization on Climate Change and the success or otherwise of the effort.

3. The Impact of Trade on Climate Change

There has been a rapid expansion of international trade and deepened trade liberalization among countries within the last few decades. The volume of world trade is nearly 32 times greater than the 1950 level. The ratio of merchandise trade to gross domestic product (GDP) has increased from less than 20 percent to more than 50 percent in less than half a century. This was partly facilitated by reductions in average world tariffs at major export destinations; that is, tariffs were reduced from 18 percent in Europe and 15 percent in North America in the late 1950s to about 4 percent in North Atlantic countries by the end of the 20th century (Baldwin 2006). In parallel, there has been a drastic increase in the carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentrations in the atmosphere, from about 310 ppm (parts per million) in the 1950s to about 390 ppm by the end of the century (World Bank 2010). The simultaneous expansion of trade, greater trade liberalization and higher pollution intensities, therefore, raise questions about the climate impacts of trade and trade liberalization.

Climate change is in turn having a significant impact on ecosystems, economies and communities. Rising average temperatures do not simply mean balmy winters. Some regions will experience more extreme heat while others may cool slightly. Flooding, drought and intense summer heat could result. Violent storms and other extreme weather events could also result from the increased energy stored in our warming atmosphere.

One of the most serious impacts of climate change is how it will affect water resources around the world. Water is intimately tied to other resource and social issues such as food supply, health, industry, transportation and ecosystem integrity. Climate change also threatens the health of our children and grandchildren through increased disease, freshwater shortages, worsened smog and more. These impacts also pose incalculable economic risks that far outweigh the economic risks of taking action today.

³Multilateral environmental agreements (MEAs), MEAs are agreements between States which establish principles, rights and obligations undertaken by parties to respect the environmental purposes. Currently are operating over 300 MEAs, whose content aims to regulate and prevent the environmental challenges through a variety of specific tools (legal, economic, technical, and commercial, etc.). About 30 of these are focused on the use of environmental trade measures.

The world's leading scientists report that to prevent dangerous levels of global warming governments should act to limit global warming to less than 2°C by taking concerted action to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. This objective appeared to have been taken seriously at the 21st Conference of the Parties to the Kyoto Protocol in France from ...the success of that COP is the core discussion of this paper. Does the outcome of the COP amount to putting old wine into new wine skin? Or is it, for once, a manifestation of unfeigned commitment to the protection of the environment for present and future generations? As a background to the above analysis, the next section will examine the interaction between international trade and environmental in the Context of Climate Change in Oman.

4. International Trade-Environment Nexus in the Context of Climate
4.1.Greenhouse Gas Emissions in Oman

In case of Oman, as oil and natural gas sectors dominates the economy in terms of their big share in GDP and government revenues, they considered to be the primary cause of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions within the country. So Oman is used to be vulnerable to impacts of increased average temperatures, less and more erratic precipitation, sea level rise (SLR) and desertification. According to study of WRI (2005) the most contributing factor to CO₂ in Oman, comes from gaseous fuels followed by liquid fuels, (see figure 1, below).

Figure 1: CO₂ emissions from gaseous fuel consumption (kt)

Source: World Bank, World Development Indicators, 2017

Another important factor for generating CO₂ emissions comes from electricity and heat production. Electricity in Oman is generated from two sources, natural gas (97.5) and oil (2.5), figure 2. Looking at the Sources of CO₂ emissions which comes from energy sub-sectors in Oman (expressed as a percentage of the total Fuel combustion), electricity ranked number one followed by manufactured sector and transportation sector (figure 3)

Figure 2: Electricity production as a percentage of fuel type in Oman, 1991–2014.

Source: World Bank, World Development Indicators, 2017

Figure 3: Sources of CO2 emissions from energy sub-sectors in Oman (expressed as a percentage of the total Fuel combustion)

Source: World Bank, World Development Indicators, 2017

4.2.Trade effects of Climate Change: Graphical Inspection

Taking into account indirect emissions via inter-industry linkages, international trade make up roughly 23% of production-based emissions in recent years (Davis and Caldeira 2010)⁴.

Figure 4 below shows the relationship between trade at aggregate level and CO2 emission (metric tons per capita). As trade fluctuates over the years 1992 -2013, the effect on CO2 emission is kept increasing over the same period.

Figure 4: Trade (% of GDP) vs. CO2 emission (metric tons per capita)

Source: World Bank, World Development Indicators, 2017

⁴ Davis and Caldeira 2010, Consumption-Based Accounting of CO2 Emissions, Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences · March 2010

Figures 5 and 6 depict the relationship between CO2 emission (metric tons per capita) and fuel exports as % of merchandized exports and GDP per capita growth (annual%) consecutively for the period 1991-2013. As shown in the graphs the CO2 emission (metric tons per capita) is increasing with increasing both the fuel exports as % of merchandized exports and GDP per capita growth (annual %)

Figure 5: The relationship between CO2 emission (metric tons per capita) and fuel exports as % of merchandized exports, 1992-2013

Source: World Bank, World Development Indicators, 2017

Figure 6: The relationship between CO2 emission (metric tons per capita) and GDP per capita growth (annual %), 1991-2013

Source: World Bank, World Development Indicators, 2017

5. The Common Response to the Impact of Trade on Global Warming

As global warming keeps calling for a common response from the international society, the Objective is also to gather a maximum number of states in one common agreement. Thus, the 1992 United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) aims to stabilize “greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system” (Article 2). It establishes common but differentiated responsibilities through the division of states into three groups with specific duties (Article 4), taking into account national, regional development priorities, and the importance of maintaining sustainable economic growth.

The Kyoto Protocol is based upon *market strategies* and above all on trade logic to achieve its goals. Article 4 provides for the globalization of emissions quotas within the countries’ group by joint fulfilment of their respective commitments. The classification of states into categories makes it more flexible and easier for economic agents to achieve the set objectives in the least expensive way. However, depending on the attribution of the set objectives, a surplus of emission rights can appear on the market, which may lead to increased emissions from the group of industrialized countries. The Kyoto Protocol establishes

emission trade between Annex I countries. This has, however, been highly criticized as “commercializing the atmosphere”.

Moreover, the Conference of the Parties to the UNFCCC decided to establish a Pilot phase allowing developed and developing countries to conclude agreements, aiming for the fulfilment of obligations related to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, by participating in investment projects. States and the private sector may be able to invest in countries in transition or in developing countries and obtain emission credits in exchange.

These emission reduction units “shall be added to the assigned amount for the transferring Party” (Articles 3.10 and 3.12).

Other techniques advocated in the Kyoto Protocol include:

- Tax impositions on carbon dioxide emissions;
- Adoption of certain treatment or emission rules, notably for greenhouse gas emissions not regulated by the Montreal Protocol;
- Elimination of subsidies and any fiscal incentive practices running counter to the objective of the Framework Convention.

The Kyoto Protocol provides for the application of trade liberalization measures to enable a state to comply with its commitments:

Progressive reduction or phasing out of market imperfections, fiscal incentives, tax and duty exemptions and subsidies in all greenhouse gas emitting sectors that run counter to the objective of the Convention and application of market instruments. (Article 2.1(a)(v), Kyoto Protocol, 1997)

The Kyoto Protocol establishes a direct link between the implementation of measures on emissions reduction and their consequences on international trade, respecting the very general principle of compatibility between the systems of rules stated in the UNFCCC. No system is intended to prevail over the other, the tendency being more towards conciliation in case of conflict. Furthermore, it states that the countries in Annex I shall limit the impact of their policies and measures on international trade:

The Parties included in Annex I shall strive to implement policies and measures under this Article in such a way as to minimize adverse effects, including the adverse effects of climate change, effects on international trade, and social, environmental and economic impacts on other Parties, especially developing country Parties.(Article 2.3, Kyoto Protocol, 1997)

The Kyoto Protocol does not only respect the principle of free trade but can be characterized by giving particular significance to the private sector regarding the implementation of the envisaged market strategies. However, their intervention may lead to problems regarding monopolies or abuse of dominant positions (for instance, if subsidiary companies under the same holding company are the only beneficiaries of subsidies and technology transfers). Issues of civil or criminal liability may also arise regarding the economic agents involved in the implementation of provisions for the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions.

This market-based pattern has been applied in all the Conferences of the Parties to the Kyoto Protocol; and so far, only negligible steps have been made to mitigate Climate Change as a result. Even regional attempts have not proven to be helpful in curbing the menace. For example, in addition to European Council’s Six Action Programs, the region has also introduced the Principle of Integration where the 1992 Maastricht Treaty enshrined the principle of integrating the environment into other Community policies in Article 130 R 2, represented in a title devoted to the environment. It simply states, “Environmental protection requirements must be integrated into the definition and implementation of other Community policies”.

Subsequently, the Amsterdam Treaty (See Articles 2, 3 & 6), which entered into force on 1 May 1999, made a significant contribution by referring to sustainable development, a concept developed by the 1987 Brundtland Report. The European institutions took this new goal into account when developing a European strategy in favor of sustainable development, consecrated by the European Council held in Gothenburg in June 2001.

In the same way, through NAFTA, North America developed a regional integration and cooperation in the areas of economy, environment and manpower, while Mercosur, aiming at the creation of a common market,

established rules and developed structures to approach environmental problems related to freedom to trade and free competition. NAFTA aims at governing the economic and trade activities of the three signatory states, by introducing rules on the reduction and elimination of custom duties, international investment, sanitary and phytosanitary norms, intellectual property, the energy, petrochemical and agriculture sectors (Chapter 7B)

6. National Climate Change Response: Oman's Climate Change Initiatives

Oman is taking serious steps to reduce its greenhouse gas emissions and global warming. The Sultanate signed the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) at the first Earth Summit in Brazil Conference in 1992, and then ratified it by the Royal Decree No. 119/94, December 7, 1994. Oman also ratified the Kyoto Protocol to the Framework Convention on Climate Change by the Royal Decree No. 107/2004, October 10, 2004. Not only that, but also established the Ministry of Environment and Climate Affairs in 2007 by the Royal Decree No. 90/2007⁵. The Ministry of Environment and Climate Affairs (MECA) established the Directorate-General for Climate Affairs, which is responsible to assess vulnerability and the risks posed by climate change and focus and intensify work in the areas of adaptation and mitigation of climate change at the national and international levels⁶.

Oman has committed to curb its expected Green House Gas (GHG) emissions growth by two per cent in a document sent by the Ministry of Environment and Climate Affairs to the UNFCCC (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change) before the landmark climate accord in Paris.

7. Taking a Bold Step: a Proposal

A number of WTO rules deal with many of the economic and regulatory instruments used by countries to mitigate climate change. However, the relevance of WTO rules to climate change mitigation policies, as well as the implications for trade and the environmental effectiveness of these measures will very much depend on how these policies are designed and the specific conditions for implementing them.

The debate on trade and climate change is taking place against the backdrop of vital multilateral climate change negotiations, which are due to come to a conclusion at the 21st Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Conference on Climate Change (UNFCCC) in December 2015 in France.

Not fixing environmental standards that are restrictive to trade is a trap in itself and will render all the above environmental protection efforts wasted. At the same time, it makes sense not to totally sacrifice development on the altar of environmental protection. Consequently, it becomes imperative to temper the two extremes to create a delicate balance (compromise).

What is needed to immediately mitigate the effects of Climate Change on the global environment is not a market based approach but an earth-based approach. If such an approach must be reflected in the Kyoto Protocol, it must be one that gets everyone in good faith to be able to implement *binding* provisions. Provisions that will review the commitments every five years, if the emission levels must reduce below 2 degrees.

Let it be emphasized also, that climate change is not just about increase in temperature; or how much developed countries are willing to support developing countries; or what part of the agreements should be binding or not.

⁵ <https://meca.gov.om/en/module.php?module=pages-showpage&CatID=21&ID=40> accessed 18/08/2018

⁶ Ministry of Environment and Climate Affairs (MECA) has established a number of monitoring systems in order to monitor and control the behavior of the environment, especially in the industrial zones. The mobile stations are located in the Sohar Industrial region (Sohar Port) and the other one in the commercial zone in Muscat (Ruwi). In addition, the Ministry installed three fixed environment monitoring stations in Al Rusail Industrial State, Sohar Industrial State, and Al Fahal Port. This framework can help, for example, to locate the controlling industrial air pollution sources, to estimate the contributions from each pollution source to pollutant concentrations at specific locations, to characterize, understand and predict quantitatively the pathways of industrial air pollutant transport.

Arguably, these are secondary concerns bordering on the ephemeral. The focus in the battle to combat climate change should begin from values – utilitarian (consumption) values do not show any meaningful commitment to saving the earth. If all that trade policies reflect are for the benefit of man in this generation, then the current attempts to curb global warming are feigned ones. A value of stewardship, of consciousness of the need for environmental preservation should be reflected in clauses that promote maintenance – clauses that acknowledge the that an absolute protection of the environment is not possible; but at the same time reckon *and* are committed to ensuring that material progress (trade) is adapted to the earth's carrying capacity.

8. Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

The analysis of climate change impacts on Oman in the context of international trade confirms the importance of understanding the unique interplay between the Omani economies and climate change in order to inform a formulation of national climate action plans.

In this paper, relations between international trade and environment have been discussed within its implications at national and internal levels. It was shown that the absence of a firm balance between the two has affected climate change.

Climate change and environmental sustainability is the big issue and challenges facing all countries nowadays. Mitigating global warming require a attention and efforts to address climate change around the world.

For country as Oman who depends mainly on oil and gas sector, the issue of reducing CO₂ emission need formulation of strict environmental and energy policies. The government can adopt and encourage the use of renewable energy as best alternatives for oil and gaz.

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